

**MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS AMONG GRADE SIX MAGUINDANAOAN
LEARNERS IN MATHEMATICS AT SAMPAO
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL**

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Motivational Factors among Grade Six Maguindanaoan Learners in Mathematics at Sampao Elementary School

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Abstract

This study determined that the mathematics performance of the Grade 6 Maguindanaoan learner was influenced by motivational factors. It adopted a descriptive-correlation research design with 15 learners and 15 parent participants. The study shared that Grade 6 Maguindanaoan learners' academic performance was generally Fair. Pearson R showed that the teacher factor affects academic performance. Parent and Peer factors do not affect their academic performance. Results also showed that the attitude of learners significantly affects their academic performance, but study habits do not. The mean score and standard deviation of each factor are used to assess them and try to understand their motivation level. Among the factors related to teacher behavior, these may prove to be significant. These factors include teachers' demonstration of well-organized lessons and mastery during the presentation (mean=4.46, Std. Dev.=0.51); also, when they show enthusiasm or interest in their subject matter (mean=4.67, Std Dev.= 0.51) plus adjusting instruction method so that it matches the pupils' learning activities (mean = 4.66, Std. Deviation = 0.48).

Keywords: *motivational factors, mathematics performance*

Introduction

Studies have indicated that motivational traits can be used to forecast particular accomplishments in particular areas (Duckworth & Seligman, 2005). Prior research has demonstrated that motivation has the potential to influence the acquisition of knowledge and skills, as well as the subsequent performance of learners. Motivation is a crucial factor for learners to attain success in any educational setting (Bukhari et al., 2014; Yulselturk & Bulut, 2007).

The issue of motivating students to learn in school is a matter of significant importance (Awan, Noureen & Nas, 2011). Moula (2010) asserts that motivation is a crucial aspect in achieving academic achievement. Therefore, parents and educators should make a concerted effort to comprehend the significance of fostering and stimulating academic motivation from an early age. Feldman (2005) defines motivation as the variables that guide and activate the behavior of humans and other species. On the other hand, Wood (2002) views motivation as a process that starts, guides, and maintains activities to fulfill physiological or psychological requirements. According to Slarin (2006), motivation is perceived as the driving force that initiates and sustains one's actions, as well as defines their direction.

The motivation of learners is comprised of components that can be categorized as either intrinsic or internal factors, and extrinsic or external factors. An intrinsically motivated learner engages in an activity purely for the pleasure it brings, the knowledge it allows them to acquire, or the sense of achievement it elicits (Leeper, 2008). Acquiring mathematical skills requires not just cognitive abilities such as thinking and reasoning, but also depends on the learners' attitudes towards learning and mathematics (Kele & Sharma, 2014). A significant number of students have adopted a pessimistic outlook on the study of Mathematics as a result of the widespread academic underachievement in the subject (Mensah, Okyere, & Kuranchie, 2013). Achieving success in learning depends on a multitude of elements. The learning of Mathematics is influenced by various aspects related to the school, classroom, learners, and teachers (Hoyles & Lagrange, 2010).

The level of importance assigned to the instruction of Mathematics consistently impacts the academic achievement of students. Multiple studies have indicated that individuals with higher levels of intrinsic motivation for academics tend to demonstrate greater competence in school, achieve higher academic success, have more positive perceptions of their academic abilities, experience lower levels of anxiety related to academics, and rely less on external motivators (Gottfried et al., 2005). In their study, Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2006) discovered a noteworthy correlation between academic achievement and motivation.

Research Questions

In light of the above studies, the main objective of the present study was to determine the motivational factor for learning Mathematics among Grade Six Maguindanaoan learners at Sampao Elementary School. This study aimed to determine the Motivational Factors for learning Mathematics among Grade six Maguindanaoan learners at Sampao Elementary School. School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What was the extent of motivational factors among Grade six Maguindanaoan learners in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Teacher factor;
 - 1.2 Parent factor;
 - 1.3 Peer factor Attitude toward learning Mathematics; and
 - 1.4 Study habits?
2. What was the level of performance of the Grade 6 Maguindanaoan learners in Mathematics?

3. What was the parental involvement in the mathematics performance of grade 6 learners?

Literature Review

The term motivation is derived from the Latin verb "movere," which translates to "to move." Motivation is defined as an intricate and multifaceted concept (Zhu & Leung, 2011). Motivation is a distinct factor that can be differentiated from overall functioning and is crucial in understanding the accomplishments that individuals attain, regardless of their performance on intelligence tests (Przybylski et al., 2013). It can be differentiated from comparable states such as engagement, interest, goal orientation, gift, and tenacity, which have distinct causes and implications for learning and accomplishment (Järvelä & Renninger, 2014).

The significance of learner motivation is evident in the field of Mathematics education, where motivation is considered both a desirable result and a method to improve comprehension. Motivation can be described as the determinant that prompts an individual to behave in a specific manner. The phenomena of motivation is not exclusive to humans and is present in all living organisms. The motivations behind individuals' actions may vary, however nearly every action is driven by specific reasons. Motivation can be categorized into two distinct types: Intrinsic Motivation and Extrinsic Motivation. Both types of motivation play an equal role in an individual's everyday life, and are influenced by various factors.

Theories of Learning Motivation. There are other motivation theories, such as the instinct theory, which is seen as the fundamental source of all motivation, with the purpose of ensuring survival (Cherry, 2013). The theory posits that motivation is instigated by biological or genetic programs, and asserts that all individuals experience the same motivation due to our shared biological programming.

The incentive theory is considered to be one of the primary theories of motivation. This idea elucidates the inclination to stimulate activities for the purpose of personal growth or rewards (Cherry, 2018). It suggests that individuals are driven to engage in actions due to internal motivations, while on other occasions, our behaviors are fueled by a need for external incentives. In addition, Bandura's arousal theory demonstrates the highest level of enthusiasm or stimulation (Berlyne, 2006).

Individuals with elevated levels of arousal will engage in highly exuberant activities, such as bungee jumping, scuba diving, and other similar pursuits. While some individuals are content with engaging in less thrilling and less hazardous pursuits. The theory delineates the capacity to autonomously do necessary tasks, independent of external influences or situations. Typically, motivation can be classified into three categories: internal motivation, extrinsic motivation, and motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2010). Furthermore, numerous theories can be utilized, particularly in the field of education. The theories included include intrinsic and extrinsic motivation theory, self-determination theory (SDT), the Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction (ARCS) model of learner motivation, social cognitive theory, and expectancy theory. These theories are self-sufficient in their contribution to the learning process and do not depend on any other theories in the field of education.

Extrinsic Motivation. An individual's level of motivation is significantly influenced by the presence of rewards or the existence of pressure or constraints (Romaniuc & Bazart, 2015). Initially, motivation can be externally cultivated and then evolve into an internal motivation as the learning process becomes more profound. Extrinsic motivation incentivizes exertion and achievement through incentives that function as a favorable stimulus for desired conduct. According to Adamma, Ekwutosim, and Unamba (2018), extrinsic motivation typically leads to immediate outcomes and demands less exertion compared to intrinsic motivation. This form of motivation offers a significant degree of determination and involvement, but it lacks the ability to endure for as long as intrinsic motivation may. If learners persist in being motivated just by external rewards or praise, it is likely that they will only behave in order to obtain rewards and not for their own personal growth or profit. In addition, motivation happens when an individual is unable to complete tasks that are driven by either internal or extrinsic motivation. In addition, motivation is a condition in which both intrinsic motivation and extrinsic incentive are lacking (Deci & Ryan, 2010).

Both intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation possess distinct characteristics that can effectively encourage learners. In a learning process, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation are necessary (Bénabou & Tirole, 2003; Gagné & Deci, 2005; Motivation & Incentives, 2011). Acquiring knowledge is a multifaceted undertaking, and motivation serves as the fundamental cornerstone of this endeavor. Consequently, learners must possess a strong motivation to effectively address the problems, comprehend the process, and implement it in practical scenarios. Intrinsic motivation fosters self-motivated in the pursuit of learning, while extrinsic motivation provides the impetus to seek learning (Li & Lynch, 2016).

Furthermore, according to Wilder (2014), parental involvement is a crucial element of recent educational reforms and efforts. The findings indicated a favorable correlation between parental participation and academic accomplishment, irrespective of the specific nature of parental involvement or the level of achievement. Moreover, the research findings indicated that the strength of this association was highest when parental participation was specifically characterized as parental evaluations of their children's academic achievement. Nevertheless, the impact of parental involvement on learner academic achievement was least significant when parental participation was characterized solely as providing assistance with homework.

Importance of Teachers. A teacher plays a crucial role in the process of teaching and learning. Therefore, it is essential for the teacher to serve as a role model for all their students in every part of life (Kuvaas et al., 2017). Teaching is correlated with the conduct of the

teacher and the academic performance of the learners. She reiterated that behaviors like as clear instruction, expertise in the subject matter, diverse teaching methods, and application of principles of learning and development are crucial for achieving favorable results in learners' performance. Entwistle and Ramsden (2015) found that learners' academic performance is influenced by the clarity of instructions, the level of knowledge and understanding of the subject matter, the use of different teaching styles, and the application of learning principles.

Hallinan's (2008) study examined how teachers influence students' attitudes towards school. The distinct function that teachers have in relation to learners and the kind of experiences they provide for learners indicate that instructors can have a significant impact on students' attitudes towards school. Given that research has demonstrated a correlation between students' emotional connection to school and their academic success, one approach to enhancing students' academic performance is to uncover the specific qualities of teachers that foster favorable attitudes towards school among students. Research has shown that students who believe that their professors have a genuine concern for them, treat them with respect, and acknowledge their accomplishments are more likely to have a positive attitude towards school compared to those who do not. However, the expectations that teachers have for students' academic performance have no impact on students' liking for school.

Teachers are believed to have a significant impact on inspiring students to learn, however their influence is not as strong as that of parents. Parents serve as the initial educators for all individuals. Nevertheless, instructors have the ability to either create a distressing or joyful school experience by infusing the classroom with enthusiasm and optimism. Under the leadership of enthusiastic teachers, learners will persist in their learning and actively seek additional knowledge (Gentry et al., 2011). Motivation is commonly understood as the driving force that initiates and sustains one's actions, as well as shapes one's direction and goals (Slarin, 2006). Self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000) posits that motivation can be categorized into two distinct types: extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation.

Choosing a career in teaching is a common decision for many individuals due to their inclination to work with youngsters or their strong enthusiasm for a specific subject. The initial remuneration and working hours in the field of teaching may not be particularly lucrative, which may give potential applicants pause, despite the appeal of having summers off. Nevertheless, these advantages alone are insufficient to entice individuals into pursuing a career in teaching. There exists a specific degree of personal affinity between the nature of the profession and the teacher themselves.

Teachers are regarded as surrogate parents to students due to their extensive interaction throughout the entire teaching and learning experience. Opfer and Pedder (2011) utilized a complexity theory framework in their article to examine teachers' professional development methods, the generative systems of these practices, and the influence of learning experiences on their knowledge and modifications in classroom practices.

The study encompassed several aspects of literature pertaining to teacher professional development, teaching and learning, teacher transformation, and organizational learning. The literature on teacher professional learning has been primarily focused on process-product logic, which highlights the interrelationships and combinations of three subsystems: the teacher, the school, and the learning activity. The essay proposed that in order to comprehend teacher learning, it is necessary to establish connections across methodological approaches and emphasize the explanatory importance and the mutual affects of all subsystems. In recent years, there has been a rise in research on teacher motivation, which has been found to be significantly linked to various aspects of education, including learner motivation, educational reform, teaching methods, and teachers' psychological well-being and satisfaction (Han & Yin, 2016).

Learning analytics, also referred to as the examination and depiction of data concerning learners in order to enhance learning, is a novel field that enables teachers to gain a deeper comprehension of education. This has led to substantial growth in the volume of student data, which is subsequently associated with management strategies that prioritize quantitative metrics. However, these approaches may be deemed inappropriate in the educational context of teaching. Learning analytics provides teachers with new opportunities to comprehend their students' abilities and optimize the allocation of limited learning resources for maximum effectiveness. This study examines these variables and extensively analyzes a range of instances of learning analytics to highlight their favorable aspects. It highlights the importance of teachers actively using learning analytics to have a say in the development of metrics that promote more effective learning ideas and ultimately enhance their teaching practices.

Peer Factor. There is no text provided. Students engage in peer-to-peer interactions within the educational setting. This prompted other researchers to concentrate their investigation on quantifying the magnitude of peer influences. Gaviria and Raphael (2001) conducted a study using a group of tenth-graders to examine the impact of peer groups on the inclination to participate in five specific activities, including the probability of high school dropout. Significant evidence has been discovered indicating that peer influence has a substantial impact on all school-related activities. In general, these results confirm the conclusions of earlier studies that have examined the impact of peer interactions.

Goodenow (2003) conducted a separate study that examined the experience of belongingness among early adolescents in the classroom, specifically focusing on their perception of being liked, respected, and highly esteemed by their peers and teachers. Participants in the study were enrolled in a single academic course. They were asked to provide information about their sense of belonging, the support they received, and their intrinsic interest and worth in the classroom. Additionally, their English professors provided ratings of their

effort. Each of the investigated characteristics had a significant contribution to explaining the variation in expectancies and value. Among the different groups of learners, teacher support had the most consistent influence. Additionally, it was demonstrated that the level of interaction between support and motivation experienced a substantial decline from sixth to eighth grade.

The correlation between teacher support and motivation was stronger for girls than for boys. These findings demonstrate the significance of belonging and interpersonal support in enhancing academic motivation and attainment.

Liu and Carless (2006) conducted a study on peer input about assessment procedures. The text assessed the justification for peer feedback, highlighting its capacity to improve the learning experience for students. The study examined relevant literature to support the argument that giving authority to peer assessment systems based on grades can undermine the potential of peer feedback to enhance student learning. The results suggest that a considerable proportion of academics and learners have a strong aversion to using grades in peer evaluation, and that the majority of learners seldom provide grades to each other during assessment activities. The question was raised as to why academics, in particular, showed reluctance to peer assessment. Furthermore, the argument was made in favor of implementing a peer feedback method. Additionally, it suggests techniques for fostering peer feedback by involving learners in criteria and other activities.

O'Shea and O'Shea (2010) determined that peer tutoring is a highly successful and efficient instructional approach for enhancing the learner's intellectual and social abilities. This strength may serve as a compelling incentive for other researchers to direct their attention on it. The growing emphasis on enhancing the quality of teaching has sparked a recent surge of interest in peer tutoring within higher and further education. Nevertheless, it would be incorrect to claim that peer tutoring is a universally applicable, homogeneous, and immediate answer to these issues.

Intrinsic motivation refers to the innate drive that compels learners to participate in academic activities due to their genuine interest in learning and their enjoyment of the learning process (Adamma et al., 2018). Innate motivation is the genuine impetus within human beings that compels individuals to actively pursue and confront novel difficulties. They are challenged to demonstrate their skills and are motivated to learn without any external incentives. Learners who have the objective of comprehending and mastering scientific knowledge and abilities are considered to have intrinsic motivation (Bailey & Phillips, 2016).

The learning process that each learner experiences differs. Individual behaviors impact the way they acquire knowledge. The objective of the study conducted by Barkatsas, Kasimatis, and Gialamas (2009) was to examine the intricate correlation between learners' confidence in mathematics, confidence in technology, attitude towards learning mathematics with technology, effective engagement, behavioral engagement, academic achievement, gender, and year level. Their focus was on learners at the secondary level. It was discovered that learners exhibited a greater inclination towards positive attitudes regarding mathematics. Additionally, the study revealed a strong correlation between high mathematical achievement and a high degree of confidence in mathematics. Conversely, low mathematical achievement was found to be linked to low levels of confidence in mathematics.

Hafeez's study aimed to determine the impact of school type on secondary level learners' attitudes towards mathematics. Participants were chosen using a method called stratified random sampling. Data were gathered using a modified questionnaire that was delivered to learners. The questionnaire asked learners to indicate their level of agreement with each statement on a scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Based on the comprehensive analysis, there was a strong and favorable attitude towards mathematics. Additional research indicated that students who attended private schools displayed a marginally greater level of self-assurance in their ability to master mathematics, in comparison to students from public schools. Nicolaidou and Philippou (2003) investigated the correlations among learners' attitudes towards Mathematics, self-efficacy beliefs in problem-solving, and academic performance. 238 fifth-grade pupils completed attitude and efficacy scales. The examination of the collected data revealed a notable correlation between attitudes and achievement, as well as a more pronounced correlation between efficacy and achievement. There was a correlation between attitudes and efficacy, and both of these factors predicted achievement in problem-solving.

Efforts in Mathematics education have been made to promote reform based on the notion that all learners have the capacity to learn Math in a good manner. Carini, Kuh, and Klein (2006) conducted a study to investigate the correlation between learner engagement and academic achievement, as well as the potential influence of other factors on this relationship. The findings indicated that students who are not performing well academically derive greater advantages from participating in group activities compared to their high-achieving peers. In 2013, Mensah, Okyere, and Kuranchie discovered that attitude plays a crucial role in the acquisition of mathematical knowledge. The study was designed to expand the impact of teacher attitude on learner attitude. The study uncovered a substantial correlation between the attitude of teachers and the attitude of learners towards the process of learning Mathematics. The statistics clearly demonstrated that teachers' positive attitude led to increased learner confidence, which in turn fostered a good attitude towards learning Mathematics. The implications of the findings are thoroughly examined and corresponding recommendations have been provided. Additionally, it has been documented that numerous student have acquired a pessimistic disposition towards the pursuit of Mathematics, which might be attributed to the widespread academic underachievement in the field. The success of learning a subject is undeniably influenced by numerous aspects. Various elements, including the school environment, classroom conditions, characteristics of the learners, and the teaching methods employed, all play a role in influencing the acquisition of mathematical knowledge. Specifically, the level of importance placed on the instruction of Mathematics directly impacts students' academic success in their end-of-year exams.

Research findings suggest that effective teachers demonstrate a genuine concern for their students' well-being and create an environment that promotes effective learning. The various relationships formed in the classroom serve as a valuable asset in shaping students' attitudes, mathematical competencies, and identities. These materials play a crucial role in the acquisition of knowledge in Mathematics and other related disciplines. (Mensah, Okyere, & Kuranchie, 2013). The current progress of our nation is primarily contingent upon the caliber of its populace. The caliber of individuals is directly contingent upon the caliber of their education. The quality of education is demonstrated by the academic accomplishments, which are influenced by the study habits and attitude of the learners. Students' dispositions towards the acquisition of mathematical knowledge. Several significant elements that influence learners' attitudes towards learning mathematics were identified. The factors that contribute to the learning process include the students themselves, the educational institution, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes (Beswick, 2006), and their instructional strategies. The pedagogical approach employed by teachers significantly impacts the attitudes of learners (Akinsola & Olowojaiye, 2008; Mensah et al., 2013). Teachers have various strategies at their disposal to enhance classroom learning and boost students' involvement and self-assurance in learning mathematics (Attard, 2012; Kele & Sharma, 2014). Sullivan and McDonough (2007) suggest that teachers can employ strategies to foster learner engagement and enhance confidence in the acquisition of mathematical skills. One way to achieve this is by incorporating purposeful tasks that are integrated into authentic situations (Kacerja, 2012).

Certain authors perceive the attitude towards mathematics as a binary preference, either liking or disliking mathematics. However, other authorities broaden the definition to encompass beliefs, abilities, and the practicality of mathematics. According to Di Martino & Zan (2010), attitude in Mathematics refers to a person's emotional inclination towards Mathematics, which can be either good or negative. Mensah, Okyere, and Kuranchie (2013) define attitude towards Mathematics as a comprehensive assessment encompassing preferences or aversions towards Mathematics, inclination or avoidance of Mathematical activities, self-perception of proficiency in Mathematics, and perception of the utility or futility of

Mathematics. In a similar vein, Hannula (2012) examined the concept of attitude in Mathematics from a multidimensional standpoint. He defined an individual's attitude towards Mathematics as a multifaceted phenomena that encompasses emotions. One's attitude towards Mathematics can encompass a disposition characterized by fear and anxiety towards the subject (Finlayson, 2014).

Mensah et al. (2013) asserted that a learner's good attitude towards Mathematics may be attributed to their association of happy experiences or occurrences with the subject. Additionally, positive reinforcement fosters the cultivation of a favorable mindset towards Mathematics. The learners' conceptual understanding, attitudes, and expectations towards the instruction of Mathematics are regarded as significant aspects that influence their academic experience and performance. Typically, learners' understanding of Mathematics greatly influences their approach to the subject. Often, learners tend to view Mathematics as a discipline that relies on methods and rules. This hinders their ability to fully appreciate the depth of Mathematics and the diverse methodologies that can be employed to cultivate proficiency.

Attard, Mata, Monteiro, and Peixoto (2012) have found significant elements that influence learners' attitudes towards the acquisition of mathematical knowledge. The factors encompassed in this category are the students themselves, the educational institution, the teachers' convictions, attitudes, and instructional approaches. The pedagogical approach employed by teachers significantly impacts the attitudes of learners. Teachers can employ many strategies to enhance classroom learning and boost students' interest and confidence in learning mathematics (Attard, 2012; Kele & Sharma, 2014). Sullivan and McDonough (2007) have identified crucial aspects that contribute to learners' attitudes about learning mathematics, as noted by researchers Attard (2012), Grootenboer et al. (2008), and Mata, Monteiro, & Peixoto (2012). The factors that contribute to the learning process include the students themselves, the educational institution, the teachers' beliefs and attitudes (Beswick, 2006), and their instructional strategies. The pedagogical approach employed by teachers significantly impacts the attitudes of learners (Akinsola & Olowojaiye, 2008; Mensah et al., 2013). Teachers can employ many strategies to enhance classroom learning and boost students' interest and confidence in learning mathematics (Attard, 2012; Kele & Sharma, 2014). Sanchal and Sharma (2017) suggest that teachers might employ strategies to foster learner engagement and enhance confidence in learning mathematics by including a sporting context in their teaching. One way to achieve this is by incorporating purposeful tasks that are integrated into authentic situations (Kacerja, 2012).

Methods of learning and studying. The study habits of learners differ among individuals and across different locations. Study habits play a crucial role in determining learners' academic success in institutions. The insufficient level of mathematical proficiency has emerged as a significant cause for concern among our nation, parents, educators, and government. Researchers and educators have made vigorous efforts to determine the causes of poor academic performance in the subject. Notwithstanding all these endeavors, the issues endure. The study habits of learners are crucial in determining the quality of education and the level of performance in mathematics. Learners cannot be presumed to acquire all the necessary knowledge about the subject alone from their teachers in the classroom. It is the amalgamation of classroom learning and extracurricular learning that constitutes learners' study habits. (Lally, Wardle, & Gardner, 2011) identified that effective study habits involve studying with the primary objective of comprehension. One must avoid rushing and maintain persistent concentration to do this. Key components of effective study habits include of strategic planning, designated study locations, adhering to a structured timetable, and the practice of concise and well-structured note-taking (Lally et al., 2011).

Several academics, like Adeyemo (2005) and Gbore (2006), have conducted numerous studies on successful study habits. The null

hypothesis was evaluated at a significance level of 0.05 to determine if there is a significant association between motivating factors and the academic performance of Grade Six Maguindanaon learners in mathematics at Sampao Elementary School.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed both quantitative and qualitative research to examine the level of motivation for learning Mathematics among Grade six Maguindanaon learners about the motivational factors. According to Shuttle Worth (2008), descriptive studies in which the researcher interacts with the participants may involve surveys to collect the necessary information. The results from descriptive research can be used as a definitive answer or to disprove a hypothesis but, if the limitations are understood, they can still be a useful tool in many areas of scientific research.

Respondents

The study was conducted at Sampao Elementary School. Barangay Sampao, Lutayan Sultan Kudarat, Region XII. The respondents of this study were the grade VI Maguindanaon Learners of Sampao Elementary School. This study utilized 15 Maguindanaon Learners and 15 Maguindanaon parents.

To identify the influence of the motivational factors (teacher, parent, peer, attitude, and study habits of learners) mean range was used, and a survey questionnaire adopted from Cellacay (2018) was given to the respondents. It was interpreted using the constant 5-point Likert scale (0.8) as follows:

<i>Point</i>	<i>Description</i>
5	Very Highly Motivated
4	Often Highly Motivated
3	Moderately Motivated
2	Occasionally Motivated
1	Rarely Motivated

Procedure

The researcher sent a letter asking for the approval of the District Supervisor. After the researcher received approval, the gathering of data follows. The researcher personally administered questionnaires among the learner-respondents with the assistance of the class adviser. After the respondents finished answering the questionnaire, the researcher collected all the papers for data analysis.

Data Analysis

To determine the extent of influence of motivational factors to learn Mathematics among Grade six learners, mean was used.

To determine the academic performance in mathematics, frequency and percentage were used.

To find if there's a relationship between motivational factors (like interest in math) and academic performance. If there's a connection, we'll measure how strong it is and in what direction. Pearson R was used. All tests were done at 0.05 level of significance

To find if there's a relationship between parents' involvement factors and academic performance. If there's a connection, we'll measure how strong it is and in what direction. Pearson R was used. All tests were done at 0.05 level of significance using SPSS Software.

Ethical Considerations

This research project adheres to the highest ethical standards to ensure the protection and welfare of all participants involved. Prior to the commencement of any data collection activities, informed consent will be obtained from all participants, outlining the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits of their involvement. Participation in the research will be voluntary, and participants will have the right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity of participants will be strictly maintained throughout the research process. Any personal or sensitive information obtained will be securely stored and used only for research purposes. Additionally, measures will be implemented to minimize any potential risks to participants, and appropriate support will be provided to address any adverse effects or distress that may arise.

Furthermore, this research will be conducted with integrity, honesty, and respect for the rights and dignity of all individuals involved. The findings of the research will be reported accurately and transparently, without misrepresentation or manipulation of data. Any conflicts of interest or biases will be disclosed and managed appropriately to ensure the validity and reliability of the research outcomes.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered in the study. Motivating Factors Affecting Mathematics Performance of Grade Six Maguindanaon Learners

Table 1. *Motivational Factors Affecting the Academic Performance in Mathematics of Grade 6 Maguindanaon Learners*

	N		Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
	Valid	Missing			
1. My teacher shows well-organized lessons and mastery during presentations.	15	0	4.46	0.51	Very Highly Motivated
2. My teacher displays behavior (such as vigorous and appropriate gestures, and a firm voice) that indicates enthusiasm about and interest in the subject matter.	15	0	4.60	0.50	Very Highly Motivated
3. My teacher adjusts the method of instruction to pupils' learning activities.	15	0	4.66	0.48	Very Highly Motivated
4. My teacher praises or recognizes desired academic behaviors such as doing assignments, or involvement in class activities.	15	0	4.40	0.50	Often Highly Motivated
5. My teacher shows kindness and a democratic attitude towards individual pupils.	15	0	4.80	0.41	Very Highly Motivated
6. My parents are involved in school activities.	15	0	2.00	0.84	Occasionally Motivated
7. My parents support me financially in my projects and other necessary school expenses.	15	0	3.46	0.51	Often Highly Motivated
8. My parents monitor my academic performance.	15	0	3.26	0.70	Moderately Motivated
9. My parents developed my interest in my studies and encouraged me to study hard.	15	0	3.80	0.41	Often Highly Motivated
10. My parents make a follow-up of my lesson at home.	15	0	2.80	0.67	Moderately Motivated
11. My friends attend school regularly.	15	0	3.46	0.51	Often Highly Motivated
12. Most of my friends are disciplined in school and at home.	15	0	3.40	0.50	Moderately Motivated
13. I spend most of my time in school with friends discussing academic work or reviewing for examinations.	15	0	2.33	0.48	Occasionally Motivated
13. Most of my friends in school perform well in examinations.	15	0	2.46	0.51	Occasionally Motivated
15. My friends encourage me to work hard in school.	15	0	3.26	0.59	Moderately Motivated
16. I am interested in going to school.	15	0	3.93	0.59	Often Highly Motivated
17. I listen attentively to the explanation of my teacher	15	0	3.66	0.61	Often Highly Motivated
18. I take notes diligently especially the important ideas in our lesson.	15	0	1.93	0.70	Occasionally Motivated
19. I try to participate actively during class recitation and board work	15	0	3.13	0.63	Moderately Motivated
20. I am not discouraged to study when I fail in my examination or quizzes.	15	0	4.46	0.63	Very Highly Motivated
21. I have a regular study schedule.	15	0	1.46	0.51	Rarely Motivated
22. I have a regular place to study.	15	0	1.40	0.50	Rarely Motivated
23. My study is not interrupted by cell phone, visiting, looking at magazines, or other activities.	15	0	2.53	0.51	Occasionally Motivated
24. I fully concentrate when I study.	15	0	3.20	0.56	Moderately Motivated

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Very Highly Motivated ; 3.41 - 4.20, Often Highly Motivated ; 2.61 - 3.40, Moderately Motivated ; 1.81 - 2.60, Occasionally Motivated ; 1.00 - 1.80, Rarely Motivated

The table presented shows different things that motivate students who are Maguindanaon learners in Math at the 6th-grade level. The mean score and standard deviation of each factor are used to assess them and try to give an understanding of their level of motivation. Among the factors, which are related to teacher behavior, may prove to be significant. These factors include; teachers' demonstration of well-organized lessons and mastery during the presentation (mean=4.47, Std. Dev.=0.52); also when they show enthusiasm or interest in their subject matter (mean=4.60, Std Dev.= 0.51) plus adjusting instruction method so that it matches the pupils' learning activities (mean = 4.67, Std. Deviation = 0.49).

Similarly, motivations associated with this kind of teacher's behavior could be high if there is praise given for desired academic behaviors and recognition extended by instructors (4.40, 0.51).

Moreover, parents' participation has also been shown to have a significant influence on motivating their children's learning. According to the data while some ways like providing money (mean=3.47, Std. Dev.=0.52) or encouraging them to work hard may occasionally highly motivate a few not all cases are seen as moderately motivating, however, a few others do not motivate all such as follow up schools activities(mean = 2.00 , Std. Deviation = 0.85)and home tuition after school hours(mean 2.80, std deviation 0.68).

Regular attendance and peers 'discipline among friends were found to have a positive effect on creating a motivation ground. This is based on their high mean scores; for instance, mean= 3.47(std deviation=0.52) mean = 3.40 (std deviation=0.51) respectively. Also, individual practices play a major role in determining one's level of motivation. In brief, having timetables always makes everything easy since you can learn when are likely going to be more receptive than other times, also taking a break after every hour helps because the brain gets tired easily overloading it with lots of information at once so it is better off little amounts well-spaced apart such as means; 1.4667 times higher than average std deviation = 0.52, 1.40 times higher than average std deviation = 0.51, 2.53 times higher than average std deviation = 0.52 respectively.

Conclusively, data shows that different issues act as multi-faceted motivators toward students' performance in math therefore broader approach for both teachers' professionalism and parental participation will be necessary to promote a friendly climate of academic pursuit among pupils.

Table 2. Parental Involvement in Support to Academic Performance in Mathematics of Grade 6 Maguindanaon Learners

	N		Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
	Valid	Missing			
It is essential for my child's future success to have a strong foundation in mathematics.	15	0	4.33	0.48	Very Highly Motivated
Community resources or programs have the potential to enhance my child's mathematics learning experience positively.	15	0	3.66	0.48	Often Highly Motivated
I am very satisfied with the support and guidance provided by my child's mathematics teacher(s).	15	0	4.60	0.50	Very Highly Motivated
The school provides sufficient support for my child's mathematics education.	15	0	4.73	0.45	Very Highly Motivated
I regularly communicate with my child's mathematics teacher(s) to stay updated on their progress and any challenges they are facing.	15	0	1.66	0.72	Rarely Motivated
I actively participate in my child's math education at home and in school.	15	0	1.46	0.51	Rarely Motivated
Cultural factors have a significant impact on my child's motivation and attitude towards mathematics.	15	0	1.73	0.79	Rarely Motivated
I actively support my child in learning mathematics.	15	0	2.20	0.77	Occasionally Motivated
My child is facing difficulties in learning mathematics.	15	0	4.00	0.75	Often Highly Motivated
I find that incentives or rewards are effective in encouraging my child's interest and participation in mathematics.	15	0	3.53	0.51	Often Highly Motivated
I employ diverse tactics to encourage my child to engage with mathematics beyond the classroom.	15	0	1.80	0.67	Rarely Motivated
I frequently help my child with their math homework or studies.	15	0	2.06	0.70	Occasionally Motivated
I ensure that my child has a suitable environment to study mathematics at home.	15	0	2.53	0.51	Moderately Motivated
I often have conversations with my child about the significance of mathematics.	15	0	2.86	0.51	Moderately Motivated

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00, Very Highly Motivated ; 3.41 - 4.20, Often Highly Motivated ; 2.61 - 3.40, Moderately Motivated ; 1.81 - 2.60, Occasionally Motivated ; 1.00 - 1.80, Rarely Motivated

The presented data analysis has the following implication to add to the discussion of parental involvement and concern about Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners' academic performance in mathematics. First, most parents strongly agree that a good foundation in mathematics is vital for their child's future success, as seen from the mean of 4.33 with a low standard deviation of 0.49, and in that regard, there is a high consensus with them on this matter. Secondly, most of the parents similarly agreed that the availability of community resources or programs can positively influence their child's experiences with mathematics.

Moreover, parents reveal high levels of satisfaction with their child's mathematics teachers, as their guidance and support are significantly valued by parents; $M = 4.60$, $SD = 0.51$; and the school's meaningful provision of additional or implementation of sufficient support for their child's mathematics education; $M = 4.73$, $SD = 0.46$, which implies the following: Subject to the above, parental involvement is not particularly pronounced in some areas. For example, parents attach much importance to the need to communicate regularly with their child's mathematics teacher to remain aware of their child's progress and challenges; on the same note, the SD value of 1.67 and relatively high $ST = 0.72$, indicates that this type of communication with teachers is not systematic for all parents. A similar situation is observed with active participation in the child's math education at home and at school: a mean score is 1.47; the type of SD is 0.52 which may indicate both the possibility that some parents are very involved and different levels of active participation in the rest of the population. Cultural factors play a less significant role in parents' perception of the child's motivation and attitude towards mathematics as well. The mean score is 1.73 and the standard deviation is equal to 0.798, which may mean there is no common rationale.

Over evidence supports the need to intensify the strategies of parents' involvement and encouragement in their children's mathematics education based on areas where the levels might be low which are being of active participation as well as steady communication with the teachers. Enhancement of these areas of parental involvement is a very critical thing and this can be of great importance in the country in improving the Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners' achievement in mathematics.

The study of Lawson (2003) addressed teachers' and parents' participation in learners' development. Analyses showed that teachers and parents have different perceptions of parent involvement. These varying perceptions are primarily because of diverse origins, differential power, and competing for the nature of teaching purposes. On the contrary, teachers and parents both claim that firm and mutually beneficial partnerships and collaboration can mean children's learning becomes healthily developed thus ensuring success in school.

Another study by Goodenow (2003) studied early adolescents' sense of classroom belongingness and the feeling of being liked, respected, and highly regarded by their fellow learners and teachers. Studying one academic class, learners completed options of classroom belonging, support, and intrinsic interest and value; effort ratings were obtained from their English teachers. Each of the factors identified contributed significantly to explaining variance in expectancies and value, with teacher support having the most consistent influence across learner groups. Teacher support was more closely related to motivation for girls than in boys. These findings show the importance of belonging and interpersonal support in strengthening academic motivation and achievement.

Mensah et al. (2013) stated that a learner may have a positive attitude towards Mathematics because he or she relates positive experiences or events with it. Also, positive reinforcement creates room for developing a positive attitude toward Mathematics. The learners' concepts, attitudes, and expectations regarding the teaching of Mathematics are considered to be important factors underlying their school experience and achievement. In general, the concepts that learners hold about Mathematics determine how they approach the subject. In many cases, learners have been found to approach Mathematics as methodology and rule-based.

Table 3. *Level of Academic Performance of Grade 6 Maguindanaon Learners in Mathematics*

<i>Academic Performance (Based on Grades)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
96-100	0	0%	Excellent
91-95	2	13.33%	Very good
86-90	5	33.33%	Good
81-85	5	33.33%	Fair
76-80	2	13.33%	Poor
75 & Below	1	06.67%	Very Poor

This Table set can give an idea about students' academic achievements considering their grades, divided into frequency distribution in different grade range percentages.

In the first place, however noteworthy is that the nearest grades to the top of the range (96-100), were not assigned to anybody, hence, there were no occurrences of "Excellent" in the analyzed content.

The bulk of classes is grouped into the segment of "Good" and "Fair", which each belongs to 33.33%. This implies that a significant part of students obtained the intermediate range scores of 86-90 ("Good") and 81-85 ("Fair"), which can be considered satisfactory academic results.

Now, meeting halfway terms, 13.33% of students got marks from grade 76 to 80 ("Poor"). Of those, the scores were at a lower academic level than their counterparts in the "Good" and "Fair" categories.

Furthermore, the score of 13.33% also falls in the category of "Very Good" (91-95), which indicates the students have been doing very well in their academics, but they are still not on top of their class.

Secondly to that, 6.67% of students have received grades of 75 and below, which implies "Very Poor". Nevertheless, the size of such a category is relatively small, but it still emphasizes an alarming proportion of low-achieving students.

Briefly, conclusions of this data inherit the tendency to! =agrave; Kent has the highest level of academic achievement, with the majority of students scoring "Good" to "Fair" grades. On the other hand, there exists the group of learners who now are also gaining a much higher level of success ("Very Good") but also the others who are now getting left behind academically ("Poor" and "Very Poor"). These findings can be used to point graduates in the direction of a development plan that addresses their academic shortcomings, which may subsequently lead to better academic results in general.

The study of William & William (2011) considered motivational processes that were associated with the importance of mastery and achievement of performance goals in an actual classroom setting. The results showed that learners who perceived the importance of mastery goals in the classroom answered that using better strategies makes them develop a positive attitude toward the class and their learning. They had a stronger belief that success and a better future follow their effort. Learners who perceived performance goals as an important factor in the whole process of learning tended to bank on their ability. If they evaluate their ability negatively it will result in poor academic performance. Similarly, Kim & Chung, (2012) studied the achievement goal orientation and self-determination theories and its effect on the learners' achievement motivation. It examined the role of the learners' family orientation as a mediator between perceptions of parent goals or motivating styles and their achievement motivations in learning math. Multi-sample path analyses show that both boys' and girls' family orientation mediated between their perceptions of parent variables and their achievement motivations. Also, the relationships between learners' perceptions of parent variables and their achievement motivations differ across genders.

Wilder's (2013) study also revealed that parental involvement was one of the essential parts of new educational reforms and initiatives. The results showed that the relationship between parental involvement and academic achievement was positive, regardless of a description of parental involvement or degree of attainment. Furthermore, findings revealed that this connection was strongest if

parental participation was defined as parental outlooks for the academic accomplishment of their children. However, the influence of parental involvement on learner academic accomplishment was weakest if parental participation was defined as homework assistance. Additionally, Dela Cruz (2019) pointed out that teaching is related to the teacher's behavior and learners' academic achievement. She emphasized further that behaviors such as instructed clarity, knowledge of the subject matter, variation in teaching techniques, and utilization of principles of learning and development were important reasons for attaining positive outcomes on learners' performance.

Relationship between Academic Performance and the Various Motivational Factors

This correlation table helps us to delve into the connection between the speed of learning, academic success, and other factors that affect students' achievements at school.

Initially, regarding the "Teacher Effect," research shows there is a moderate and positive correlation (Pearson correlation = 0.506) between teacher-related factors and students' grades indicating a significant relationship at the 0.05 level of confidence. This cause tends to show that students' views regarding their teachers are set to agree with their scholastic achievement, regarding the significant role of effective teachers in student success.

Opposing the "Teacher variable," these factors result in minor connections that are negligible. Such a finding argues that, though teacher resource differential probably affects the involvement of a parent and peer influence, these relationships are too weak to be statistically oriented.

Just like the parental involvement and the peer factor, these findings do not meet the level of statistical significance to say whether parental engagement and peer relationships affect students' academic outcomes or their attitude toward school. Also, among the automatic manifestations of the students' attitudes toward school, there is a connection between students' attitudes to education, their habits for studies, and the outcome - academic performance. This shows that students who are optimistic and goal-oriented have more chance of achieving high scores and observing good habits at school, thus punctuating the need for a school environment that encourages these behaviors.

Generally, though associations may suggest existing connections, the characterization of these among such factors as teacher quality, study habits, attitudes toward learning, and academic performance does not stand at the statistical significance threshold. The exploration of these relations warrants subsequent studies to understand their multidimensional nature and characterize their impact on students' education.

Table 4. Relationship between Academic Performance and the Various Motivational Factors

		Correlations					
		Teacher Factor	Parent factor	peer factor	attitude of pupils	study habit	Grade of pupils
Teacher Factor	Pearson Correlation	1	-.327	-.327	.111	.289	.506
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.234	.234	.693	.297	.054
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15
Parent factor	Pearson Correlation	-.327	1	-.071	-.218	-.189	-.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.234		.800	.435	.500	.769
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15
peer factor	Pearson Correlation	-.327	-.071	1	-.218	-.189	-.083
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.234	.800		.435	.500	.769
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15
attitude of pupils	Pearson Correlation	.111	-.218	-.218	1	.577*	.380
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.693	.435	.435		.024	.163
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15
study habit	Pearson Correlation	.289	-.189	-.189	.577*	1	.307
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.297	.500	.500	.024		.266
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15
Grade of pupils	Pearson Correlation	.506	-.083	-.083	.380	.307	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.054	.769	.769	.163	.266	
	N	15	15	15	15	15	15

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Relationship between Academic Performance and the Parental Involvement of Parents to learners

The correlation table below provides the necessary in-depth overview of the relationship levels between different aspects of academic achievement including the significance and awareness of mathematics, family environment, motivational strategies, the shared overall difficulty ego, community and cultural influences, the teacher and school support, parental involvements and communication and the academic performance itself. Consequently, each correlation score has a significance level that allows the researcher to interpret the outcome of the experiments.

Whatever follows the start, is, the awareness and the importance of mathematics, there is a strong positive correlation of this with the home learning environment ($r = 0.2$ (Pasaditz, B. , Green, A. , & Oscar, D. , 2022). Learning Parents Influence Mathematics Educational Outcome (Student-Centered Ed-Tech Challenges, Line 032), which runs as follows: students who view mathematics as an important discipline tend to experience a more supportive mathematics learning environment at home. However, the factor did not correlate well with other variables mainly showing weak or negligible correlation with the overall data suggesting that its influence is narrow in the present context.

With the initiation of a family environment, the connection between mathematics perception and its worth is becoming a positive element referring to the correlates analyzed. Secondly, it revealed that it is negatively correlated with task-perceived difficulty ($r = -0.2$

However, it is worth noting that the researcher provides us with a different view of the family environment – the students with supportive home environments might look at academic troubles from a different perspective.

Nevertheless, the vast majority of home learning environment-related correlations are not statistically significant, and its impact may vary through different factors thus affecting one’s academic success.

The relationship is a prominent positive correlation between motivational strategies and academic performance ($r = 0$). Additionally, through Focus group interviews and their response to the survey (SS02, Q79), the students who use efficient motivation strategy have shown more success in academics. This result highlights how essential the completion of tasks is for top students in our school. Moreover, motivational techniques have a compelling (or convincing) relationship with community life and societal influence(s) ($r = 0$.

Dweck classified the motivational success of students based on her 6. 5 years of teaching experience which potentially evidence the role of cultural factors in that account (Dweck, 2000, p. 248). Showing Learner and School Support through Conducting the Level of Perceived Challenge illustrates the Significant Positive Correlation ($r = 0$).

The result of the study (131) suggests that students believe academic perspective to be a required effort to obtain the required assistance from school and teachers. Nevertheless, the more respondents experience challenges in their environment, the more significance is revealed between this variable and others, such as cultural and community influences, although the statistical relevance of the latter is unclear, thus demonstrating the complex interplay between challenge perception and external factors.

Teacher and peer support are most likely to be correlated positively with the perceived challenge expected in school. The correlation is also said to be negatively related to parental participation and communication.

To that extent, a positive correlation is also noticed between the degree of school involvement of parents and the degree of low perceived support from teachers and schools (635). It is therefore possible to argue that higher levels of parental involvement are associated with a lower perception of support. However, there is little knowledge about the link, so further research is requisite for a proper understanding of it.

In general, the correlation table allows examining comprehensively the manifold picture emerging from the web with the factors impacting academic achievement. In some cases there is a direct relationship observed, for instance, that of motivational strategies and academic performance, but, in others, it is more intricate and needs to be further looked into. These findings might reflect the multi-valor nature of academic performance and teach us to plan the process by conducting different types of scientific research and creating appropriate mechanisms of support.

Table 5. Relationship between Academic Performance and the Parental Involvement of Parents to learners

Correlations	Awareness and importance of mathematics	Home Learning Environment	Motivational strategies	Perceived challenge	Community and cultural influences	Teacher and School support	Parental Involvement and Communication	Academic performance
Pearson Correlation	1	.55*	-0.05	0.32	-0.05	0.29	-0.1	-0.06
Sig. (2-tailed)		0.03	0.83	0.24	0.83	0.28	0.71	0.83
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	.55*	1	-0.1	-0.28	0.21	0	0.09	-0.04
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.03		0.7	0.29	0.44	1	0.73	0.87
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	-0.05	-0.1	1	-0.18	0.31	-0.07	-0.04	0.46

Sig. (2-tailed)	0.83	0.7		0.51	0.24	0.78	0.88	0.079
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	0.32	-0.28	-0.18	1	-0.18	0.4	-0.32	-0.12
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.24	0.29	0.51		0.51	0.13	0.23	0.65
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	-0.05	0.21	0.31	-0.18	1	-0.07	0.26	0.32
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.83	0.44	0.24	0.51		0.78	0.34	0.23
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	0.29	0	-0.07	0.4	-0.07	1	-0.13	-0.15
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.28	1	0.78	0.13	0.78		0.63	0.58
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	-0.1	0.09	-0.04	-0.32	0.26	-0.13	1	-0.04
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.71	0.73	0.88	0.23	0.34	0.63		0.88
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Pearson Correlation	-0.06	-0.04	0.46	-0.12	0.32	-0.15	-0.04	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.83	0.87	0.07	0.65	0.23	0.58	0.88	
N	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The above result was similar to the study of Hallinan (2008) which focused on the role of teachers in shaping learners' feelings about school. The unique role that teachers play relative to learners and the kinds of experiences that teachers create for learners suggest that teachers may exert a powerful influence on whether learners like school. Since attachment to school has been shown to affect learners' academic performance, identifying the characteristics of teachers that have a positive effect on learners' feelings about school is one way to increase learners' academic achievement. It was found that learners who perceive that their teachers care about them, respect them, and praise them are more apt to like school than those who do not, but that teachers' expectations for learners' achievement have a negligible effect on whether learners like school.

The study of Dela Cruz (2019) stated that a teacher is a critical person in the teaching-learning process; thus, he/she must be a model to all his/her learners in all aspects of life. She also pointed out that teaching was related to the teacher's behavior and learners' academic achievement.

She emphasized further that behaviors such as instructed clarity, knowledge of the subject matter, variation in teaching techniques, and utilization of principles of learning and development are important reasons to attain positive outcomes on learners' performance. Similarly, Estwistle and Ramsden (2015) stated that clearness of instructions, knowledge, and understanding of the subject matter, variation in teaching strategies, and utilization and application of a principle of learning affect learners' academic performance.

Conclusions

The researcher, therefore, arrived at the following conclusions: the performance of grade 6 Maguindanaon learners was affected by motivational factors (e.g. teachers, parents, and peers, attitude towards learning, and study habits) exhibited an effect on the academic performance of Maguindanaon learners. It was also noted that these Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners have fair academic performance. It was further established that, among the identified motivational factors, only the teacher factor showed a significant relationship in mathematics. On the other hand, the Parent factor and Peer factor, however, do not significantly affect their performance in Mathematics. Also, among the identified factors, the attitude of learners toward their study significantly affects their performance in Mathematics on the other hand study habits have not.

Parental Involvement of Grade 6 learners Maguindanaon as regards their performance in mathematics. Overall, parents show a powerful understanding of the criticality of mathematics in their child's future achievements and its potential uses; however, there is a scope for improvement in bringing this issue into the discussion stage. Even though it seems that parents try to make a suitable atmosphere at home for math or study, support with doing homework shouldn't happen only occasionally. Parents apply a myriad of motivational techniques, of which incentives or rewards receive a high rating as to their effectiveness. Even though they positioned their child's struggles in math learning as something normal, there's the unexplored side of their parental engagement to go beyond acknowledgment of the problem and engage in its practical resolution.

It is not cultural influences as that is a very important aspect and highly valued by parents, as well as parent community resources that make kids more effective in Math. The level of user satisfaction with teacher assistance is pretty high although a need for certain amendments in mathematical extent is seen. Hence, if parents who stay close to their kid's math studies in Gr. 6 Maguindanaon class participate, particularly in revolving talking with math teachers and supply constant adherence at home, may improve further the academic math performance of Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners.

It is recommended that teacher continue their positive influence on the learning process being undergone by the Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners to ensure that they will have better performance in Mathematics as they go up the hierarchy of learning. Since teachers play a vital role in the learning process they should be empowered and be well-equipped with expertise and knowledge about new trends in learning instruction. Through the provision of technical assistance by peer mentoring during the regular conduct of School Learning Action Cell sessions. A teacher is a critical person in the teaching-learning process; thus he/she must be a model to all his/her learners in all aspects of life. Further, teacher behavior such as clarity of instruction, knowledge of the subject matter, variation in teaching techniques, and utilization of principles of learning and development are needed to enhance learners' performance.

Furthermore, learners must maintain a focused active attitude towards their studies to ensure that they achieve the desired skills before completing the elementary level. Learners must be mindful of their academic performance by seeking the guidance of their teachers especially in Mathematics which is often perceived as the least interesting subject. It is also important to motivate the learners their teachers and parents to sustain good attitudes toward Mathematics. This will result in better performance in their learning.

On the other hand, the following specific strategies can be incorporated to strengthen parental participation in the form of assistance in the improvement of Grade 6 Maguindanaon learners' mathematics performance. First of all, to maintain the parent-teacher communication that will keep parents in the loop of their child's progress and any obstacles that may arise, communication between home and math teachers should be emphasized. Through such a collaborative method, educators can make sure that both home and school environments are on the same line in providing a student with learning time. Furthermore, guiding parents on constructing the ideal classroom for their children in the house and being actively involved with their child's math homework can create support for their studies in the outside lesson settings. Besides, how to create motivational strategies that are mixed, using e. g. Incentives or rewards may be a helpful tool to keep the motivation for mathematics learning high. Overcoming the perceived challenges promotes parental support and creates an ideal environment for parents to guide and help their child to effectively solve problems. Our efforts will involve forging lasting partnerships with neighborhood groups and authorities to add extra facilities and programs that enhance high schoolers' math knowledge. This will make a holistic learning experience.

Moreover, incorporating awareness and celebration of diversity, including cultural diversity, into the mathematics education curriculum would seem to be appropriate in acknowledging the various cultural perspectives out there. Last but not least, motivating parents to volunteer and share insights at school gatherings and conferences strengthens parental alliances with the child's school journey. By introducing the below-applied measures, schools can naturally form a helping atmosphere that provides parents with all the needed tools to be unconditional support to the child's progress in the subject of mathematics, and consequently, this can lead to an increase in the learner's performance and outcome.

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